

Regional Anatomical Study of Thodu Varma Points over the Upper ExtremityA. Muneeswaran¹, P. Kamali², K. Arumugam³, C. Kalai Kumar⁴¹Professor & HOD, Department of Varma Maruthuvam, Government Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai, Tamil Nadu²PG Research Scholar, Department of Varmam Maruthuvam, Government Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai, Tamil Nadu³Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu⁴M.B.B.S, D.Ortho, Tutor, Department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

Siddha medicine is a traditional system of medicine that originated in South India, particularly in Tamil Nadu. It's known for its unique approach to health and wellness. Varmam therapy, the crown of Siddha system of medicine, offers a drugless alternative to alleviate various ailments. The word Varmam means "Science of motion and function of the Bio-energy". Varmam therapy involves the manipulation of specific points (Varmam points) on the body to regulate the flow of bio energy (Prana). There are 108 important varmam point found in the human body. These are the reasons why a person dies, lives, falls ill, gets cured, and becomes healthy. The therapy is non-invasive and emphasizes a holistic approach to health. Varmam is classified as padu varmam, thodu varmam, thattu varmam, ull varmam, nokku varmam, meithendakalam. This article will reveal the knowledge about anatomical correlation of thodu varmam points of upper extremity. This study will be beneficial to further research.

Keywords: Siddha, Varmam, Bio-energy, Thodu Varmam points, Upper Extremity, Anatomy.

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Introduction

Varma medicine one of the special medicines in the siddha system that originated in Tamilnadu the Indian sub-continent. Varma medicine is belonging to very distant past about five thousand years ago. Varma is the "hand medicine" that sought remedies with the fingers even before man started using plant, chemical and animal materials for medicine.

Over time, it has developed uniquely as the "Varma System of Medicine" by adopting many internal and external medicines. Varma medicine is a unique medicine that contains many rare medicines, rare medical techniques and basic philosophies. Varma points are mainly 108 in number. Twelve (12) padu varma points and ninety six (96) thodu varmam points. Thodu varmam points are stimulated by touch, press and other manipulation techniques for therapeutic purpose. Thodu varmas are located at the junctions of muscles, tendons, ligaments, nerves, blood vessels, bones, etc. The book "Vama Gurunadi" refers to thodu varmas as "nerve-related". The thodu varmam points in each upper extremity are 13 in number.

Aim of the study

To locate the various Thodu varmam points over the upper extremity anatomically and the various underlying structures.

Materials and Methods

During dissection session of 1st MBBS students in the department of Anatomy, Tirunelveli Medical College, Tirunelveli, the various Thodu varmam points over the upper extremity stated in various Siddha varma books were located and the underlying anatomical structures were studied.

Observations of various Thodu varmam points over the Upper extremity**1) Puja Varmam****Synonyms**

Puya varmam (Varma soothiram- 101), Pusa varmam (Adiarma sootcham- 500), Puja varmam (Varma laadasoothiram- 300) and A.L₁₀.T₁ (Anatomical name)

Figure 1:

Location

- At the junction of upper limb and the trunk or body.
- Anterior aspect of shoulder joint. Just lateral to the acromioclavicular joint.
- **Underlying Bones** - Acromian process and Greater tubercle

- **Underlying Muscles** - Deltoid and Supraspinatus
- **Underlying Vessels**

Artery- Acromial branch of thoracoacromial artery
suprascapular artery

Vein- Acromial branch of thoracoacromial vein,
suprascapular vein

Figure 2:

2) Kai Chulukku Varmam

Synonyms

Chulukku varmam (Vama soothiram- 101, Varma thuravukol), Kai chulukki varmam ((Varma laadasoothiram- 300), Ull surukku varmam (Prana

adkkam), Puyanadukku varmam and P.L.UIS-5 (Anatomical name)

Location

Medial side of arm two finger breadth from middle of the shaft of humerus.

Figure 3:

- **Underlying Bones** – Mid-shaft of humerus
- **Underlying Muscle** – Biceps brachii

- **Underlying Nerve** – Ulnar nerve
- **Underlying vessels** – Brachial artery and Basilic vein

Figure 4:

3) Kai Kotchu Varmam

Synonyms: Kotchu varmam (Varma nithanam-500), Am.L1.UIs-8 (Anatomical name)

Location: Just behind the middle of the axilla

Figure 5:

- **Underlying Bone** - Upper part of shaft of humerus
- **Underlying Muscle** – Triceps
- **Underlying Nerve & Underlying vessels** - Ulnar nerve and Brachial artery

Figure 6:

4) Kai Muttu Kotchu Varmam

Synonyms: Kai narambu adangal (Sathuramani soothiram -600), PmL1UIa-12 (Anatomical name)

Location: Behind elbow near the medial side depression formed by olecranon

Figure 7:

- **Underlying bone** - Olecranon of Ulna and medial epicondyle of humerus
- **Underlying muscle** - Triceps brachii, Flexor digitorum profundus and Flexor carpi ulnaris
- **Underlying Nerve** - Ulnar nerve and Branches from medial cutaneous nerve of forearm
- **Underlying vessels** - Posterior ulnar recurrent vessels and Superior and Inferior Ulnar collateral vessels

Figure 8:

5) Kai Muttu varmam

Synonyms: Muttu varmam (Varma soothiram-100), Moottu varmam (Varma odivu murivu sarasoothiram- 1200), Muzhangai muttu varmam (Varma viralalavu nool), Muttu mozhi varmam

(Varma laadasoothiram- 300), Muzhangaimuttu-kaimandai varmam (Varma noolalavu soothiram-50)

Location: Behind the elbow at the level of tip of olecranon process of ulna

Figure 9:

- **Underlying Bone** - Olecranon of the ulna
- **Underlying muscle** - Triceps muscle
- **Underlying Nerve** - Ulnar nerve
- **Underlying vessels** - Posterior ulnar recurrent vessels and Superior and Inferior Ulnar collateral vessels

Figure 10:

6) Mulamkai Varmam

Synonyms:

Visamanibantha varmam (Varma soothiram- 101), Visabantha varmam (Varma aani- 108), Nadukku varmam (Varma noolalavu nool), Annalatchumi varmam (Varma kandi-urainadai), Manibantha varmam (Varmani naalumathirai), Muzhangai

varmam (Varma nithanam- 500), Indiravathi varmam (Varma vithi), Kuthirai varmam (Varma saari -205), Thamaraka varmam (Varma aani -100) and P.L.U_{f,a-8} (Anatomical name)

Location: Middle of the back of the forearm

Figure 11:

- Underlying bone - Middle of the posterior surface of Radius and Ulna
- Underlying muscle- Extensor digitorum, Extensor digiti minimi and Extensor carpi ulnaris
- Underlying Nerve - Posterior cutaneous branch of forearm and Posterior interosseous nerve
- Underlying vessels - Posterior interosseous vessels

Figure 12:

7) Kai Kannu Varmam

Synonyms: Kannu varmam (Vaarma noolalavu nool), Kaikannu varmam (Varma aani - 108) and L.C.U_{f,a-16} (Anatomical name).

Location: Points in front of the wrist corresponding to little finger and Thumb

Kai Kannu Varmam

Figure 13:

- **Underlying bone** - Medially Pisiform and Laterally Scaphoid
- **Underlying muscle** - Flexor retinaculum
- **Underlying Nerve** - Medially ulnar nerve
- **Underlying vessels** - Medially Ulnar artery and Laterally Radial artery

Figure 14:

8) Thuthikkai Varmam

Synonyms Thuthikkai varmam (Varma soothiram-101), Kozhikaluthu-agatharai varmam (Varma noolalavu nool, Varma viralalavu soothiram-50),

Agamanibantha varmam, Agamanikattu varmam, Thuthi varmam and A.L.U_{f.a}-16 (Anatomical name)

Location: Central of transverse crease in front of the wrist

Figure 15:

Thuthikkai Varmam

- **Underlying bone** - Lunate and Triquetral carpal bones
- **Underlying muscle** - Tendon of Palmaris longus
- **Underlying Nerve** - Palmar cutaneous branch from median nerve
- **Underlying vessels** - Palmar carpal arch

Figure 16:

9) Thadchany Kalam

Synonyms: Sorna thetchana kalam (Varma vilakkam), Thadchany kalam (Varma laada soothiram-300), Sorna kalam (Naalumathirai thiravukol-50), Thetchany kalam (Urpana saari-500), Thetchany edukkum kalam and Am.L0-1.U1h-4 (Anatomical name).

Location: In the palm of the hand over the distal palmar crease the point in between middle finger and ring finger

Figure 17:

- **Underlying Bone** - Metacarpal of middle and Ring finger
- **Underlying Muscle** - 3rd palmar interosseous and Adductor pollicis
- **Underlying Nerve** - Digital branch of ulnar nerve and median nerve
- **Underlying Vessels**- Palmar digital arteries branches from Superficial palmar arch

10) Kai- Kavali Varmam

Synonyms: Kavalikalam (Varma soothiram- 101), Kavaradangal (Varma adngal vivaram), Sippiram (Varma vithi) and Pl.L3.U1h-3 (Anatomical name)

Location: Over the dorsum of the hand a point in between Thumb and Index finger

Figure 18:

- **Underlying Bone** - Metacarpal of thumb and index fingers
- **Underlying Muscle** - 1st Dorsal interosseous
- **Underlying Nerve** - Dorsal digital nerves from Superficial branch of radial nerve
- **Underlying vessels** - 1st Dorsal metacarpal artery branch from radial artery

Figure 19:

11) Kai Peruviral Miya Varmam

Synonyms

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Peruviral miya varmam (Varma aani-108), Peruviral matthi varmam (Varma nithanam- 500), Idasuzhi varmam (Varma kandi- Urainadai) and PIL₃₋₄ UI_{h4} (Anatomical name)

Location

Point middle of the dorsum of thumb

Kai Peruviral Miya Varmam

Figure 20:

- **Underlying Bone** - Proximal and Distal Phalanx
- **Underlying Muscle** - Extensor pollicis brevis and Extensor pollicis longus
- **Underlying Nerve** - Dorsal digital branch from Radial nerve
- **Underlying vessels** - Princeps pollicis artery from radial artery and Dorsal digital veins

Figure 21:

12) Kai Naduviraladi Varmam

Synonyms: Nadu viraladi varmam (Varma nithanam –300), Nadu viraladiyidai varmam

(Varma nithanam- 500) and PmL₁UI_{h5} & PIL₁UI_{h5} (Anatomical name)

Location: Base of middle finger on the dorsum of hand

Kai Naduviraladi Varmam

Figure 22:

- **Underlying Bone** - Proximal phalanx of Middle finger
- **Underlying Muscle** - Dorsal interosseous and Lumbricals
- **Underlying Nerve** - Dorsal digital branches from Radial nerve
- **Underlying vessels** - Dorsal digital arteries from dorsal metacarpal arteries

Figure 24:

13) Manikkattu Varmam

Synonyms: Manikkattu varmam (Varma beerangi-100), Manikkattu bantha varmam (Adivarma sootcham-500), Ettellu poruthu varmam (Varma

nithanam -500), Kozhikaluthu puratharai varmam (Varmamnoolalavu soothiram-50)

Location: Middle of the dorsal aspect of the Wrist joint

Manikkattu Varmam

Figure 25:

- **Underlying Bone** - Carpal bones mainly dorsal surface of Lunate and Triquetrum
- **Underlying muscle** - Extensor Retinaculum
- **Underlying Nerve** - Termination of Posterior cutaneous branch of forearm and Dorsal branch from Ulnar nerve
- **Underlying vessels**- Dorsal digital venous plexus and Dorsal carpal branches from both ulnar & Radial artery

Figure 26:

Discussion

In today’s world, Varmam and its manipulation techniques are easy and powerful in the Siddha medicine when the regional anatomical location of the varmam points are well known. It is easy to treat diseases correctly administrating the force and depth of pressure. By applying pressure over the above said 13 various Thodu varma points, we can able to reduce different symptoms of various disease.

In Puja varmam point, if we give pressure will reduce the pain symptoms of the shoulder diseases. Pressure over the Kai Chulukku Varmam will reduce pain and disability of shoulder joint. In Kai Kotchu Varmam points if we give pressure, it will reduce cramps and sprains. Applying pressure over the Kai Muttu Kotchu Varmam points will relieve neuralgia and sprain due to cervical spine diseases. In Kai Muttu varmam points and Mulamkai Varmam by applying pressure will reduce the pain

due to diseases of elbow joints. Pressure over the Kai Kannu Varmam will alleviate the pain symptoms due to diseases of wrist joint. Finger pain, wrist pain, Psychotic disorders and insomnia are relieved by applying pressure over the Thuthikkai Varmam points. By applying pressure over the Thadchany Kalam points will reduce pain over the lateral aspect of the hand. Pressure over the Kai- Kavali Varmam points will reduce the symptoms of epilepsy, cervical spondylosis, eye diseases and facial palsy. Thumb dislocation symptoms are relieved by giving pressure over the Kai Peruviral Miya Varmam points. In Kai Naduviraladi Varmam if we give pressure the point will reduce the finger pain, headache, toothache. Pressure over the Manikkattu Varmam points will reduce finger pain and symptoms of wrist joint diseases.

Conclusion

Thodu varmam points are the minor energy storage points in the human body. These points are believed to be connected to the peripheral nervous system and are used in varmam therapy to stimulate energy flow and treat various diseases. In thodu varmam points the anatomical locations and structures are very important for therapeutic usage. Anatomical location, pathway and standardization are important for applying pressure to thodu varmam points. Then these anatomical locations of upper extremities are useful for cure the diseases and further evaluation of research.

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